

Hybrid manufacturing of a 3D-shaped fiber metal laminate

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ABSTRACT

This contribution presents a methodology for designing, manufacturing, and testing of a multi-material solution demonstrator of a lower control arm for electric vehicle (EV) chassis made of a three-dimensional Fiber reinforced polymer-Metal Laminate (FML). The Integrated Computational Materials Engineering (ICME) approach includes simulation methodology for process modeling, i.e. forming and draping, and part performance with the aim to reduce the developing time and related trial and errors.

The challenges, besides a limited availability of resources and material input data for numerical models, include the combination of different forming methods for Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymers (GFRP) and sheet metals (aluminum alloy) with the aim of simultaneous forming of both materials. Especially the sheet metal forming needed several improvement steps regarding heat treatment state to increase the ductility and reduce crack propagation, as well as optimization of the shape of the blanks to be formed into an asymmetric, three-dimensional geometry. Assembly includes adhesive bonding of the flat FML to the curved structure, and adapters for the testing to be performed. The quasi-static misuse testing is in good agreement to the results obtained from the simulated structural performance, with the weakest location being the adhesive bond line. An outlook on potential improvements regarding process simulation for manufacturing Fiber Metal Laminates, including necessary input data, is provided.

1. Introduction

The European Union aims to be the first climate-neutral continent by 2050 [1] and part of the responsibility to fulfill this ambitious goal lays on the automotive industry. In the development of electric vehicles (EVs), the pressure has been to increase resource-efficiency through eco-design and circular economy. This urges the need for developing advanced lightweight material systems that go beyond existing solutions. To reduce the environmental impact from production of materials, industry is shifting from mainly focusing on reducing the use-phase emissions throughout the whole life cycle. This involves analyzing extraction and processing phase of materials, manufacturing, and assembly of parts, as well as use, and end-of-life, i.e., circular use, repair, or/and recycling. As an example, the aluminum 6000 series (Al-Mg-Si) is mostly used for structural parts in the automotive industry, but their production (similarly to other grades of aluminum) results in high environmental impact. Introducing a higher amount of scrap in the aluminum production process is therefore crucial to reduce the climate

impact, without compromising the mechanical performance [2]. To further reduce the amount of aluminum towards a multi-material approach, Fiber Reinforced Polymers (FRP) are often introduced. Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRP) is a common material system for high-performance applications due to its high stiffness and high strength in combination with low weight. The drawbacks of using CFRPs, compared to Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymers (GFRP), are high cost- and environmental impacts, mainly connected to the production of carbon fibers [3].

The industry-wide suggested multi-material approach for the lightweighting of present and future generations of EVs conflicts somehow with the ambition to increase resource circularity in the automotive industry. Manufacturing scrap in the form of mixed materials can be problematic if aimed to be reused. Recycling of such materials systems also creates some challenges related to material separation and recovery at end-of-life [4]. Nonetheless, the hybrid/multi-material approach is expected to be predominant in the future as it promises to achieve a better balance in performance, weight, and affordability [5].

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A lot of work has been done to reduce the vehicle's weight using a multi-material approach. This originates several decades back in the aviation industry using Fiber Metal Laminates (FML) [6] such as GLARE [7]. The potential and benefits of using FML have been shown for the use in aerospace [8], specifically regarding damage tolerance and fatigue behavior [7,9]. Additional elastomer interlayers to improve the vibration and damping characteristics of CFRP Elastomer Metal Laminates have been investigated in [10]. A review on forming technologies of Fiber Metal Laminates is presented in [6]. Besides flat (two-dimensional) structures, manufacturing of three-dimensionally curved Fiber Metal Laminate structures is extensively investigated in the literature and still proves difficult [11–14].

This contribution is part of the recently completed European project Fatigue4Light which focused on fatigue modeling and fast testing methodologies to optimize part design and to boost lightweight materials deployment in chassis parts [15,16]. The goal was to reduce vehicle chassis weight compared to the current solutions, considering eco-design and circular economy aspects. These aspects usually involve developing several ideas, assessing their environmental impact, and then selecting a lightweight design of the lowest impact on the environment compared to conventional solutions. The reduction of production steps to develop multi-materials is crucial to increase product sustainability by reducing climate impact, production time and costs in the automotive industry. However, the processes, which involve composite materials (due to their nature) require several steps to obtain the final part. To lead the way to a single-step process, significant effort was put on the integration of technologies and processes through design and sustainability assessments.

This contribution presents a methodology of designing, manufacturing, and testing of a multi-material solution for a lower control arm as prototypical demonstrator, serving as a potential replacement of an existing steel solution. The main aims to fulfill include the affordable product to be manufacturable, easy to assemble, and that it fulfills the function. Due to the prototype character of the demonstrator chosen, the focus is on a feasibility rather than an optimization study regarding reduction of process times and materials chosen. The Integrated Computational Materials Engineering (ICME) approach presented, aims for a reduction of the developing time for EV chassis parts. Thereby, the focus is on the experimental manufacturing and testing investigations, which are supported by simplified simulation strategies for process modeling (i.e. forming and draping) and part performance. The challenges, besides a limited availability of resources and material input data for numerical models, include the combination of different forming methods for Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymers (GFRP) and sheet metals (aluminum alloy) with the aim of a simultaneous three-dimensional forming and co-curing of a GFRP core with aluminum skins.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Material data

Selcom EBX400 E-glass fiber, non-crimped fabrics (NCF), depicted in Fig. 1, with properties listed in Table 1, were impregnated with an epoxy prepreg system from Huntsman, based on chemical B-stage, using the constituents and mix ratio listed in Table 2. The biaxial $\pm 45^\circ$ layout is stitched with texturized polyester yarns, see Fig. 1 [17].

The impregnation operation was performed manually by hand-layup in atmospheric pressure with resin to fiber ratio by weight 40/60. The B-stage curing was performed at room temperature for 24 h, then the material was moved to freezer for storage at -22°C until further use.

Table 3 lists the mechanical properties of the prepreg resin system.

See [19,20] for quasistatic properties of GFRP of different layouts, manufactured under the same conditions.

Aluminum sheets, AA6082-T6 and AA6181-T6, an aluminum alloy with high content of scrap, with a thickness of 0.8 mm were supplied from Profilglass. A comparison of the mechanical behavior under quasi-

static loading (at room temperature) for both aluminum alloys is shown in Fig. 2.

The basic principle of the Fiber Metal Laminate is depicted in Fig. 3.

A prepreg stack was manufactured with a nominal thickness of 2 mm. Aluminum sheets of 0.8 mm were waterjet cut, stacked with the prepreg and a thin polyester liner according to Fig. 3.

The polyester non-woven surface veil, $A_w = 45\text{ g/m}^2$, with a dry thickness of 0.2 mm, was added on each side of the prepreg to create a resin rich surface layer, interface resp., for improved bonding between GFRP and aluminum. The full impregnation of the surface veil was done during the pressing by its absorption of excess resin from the prepreg.

During three-dimensional forming of the FML, a layer of a low-friction textile, to facilitate the sheet metal forming process (and to avoid tool wear and galling between the tool and the aluminum), was placed between the steel die surface and the aluminum. The type of low-friction textile, specially adapted for optimizing metal forming operations, was a UHMWPE non-woven tissue, $A_w = 160\text{ g/m}^2$, of the patented brand “Tribotextil” from Tribotextil AB [21].

2.2. Manufacturing details

The press used for manufacturing is from AP&T, Model ODEN-FTS-12000/(19000), see Fig. 4, with a maximum force of 1200 ton, upgradeable to 1900 ton and a press table of $2200\text{ mm} \times 3000\text{ mm}$.

The daylight (maximum opening) is 2200 mm with a stroke of 1600 mm. The maximum closing speed is 350 mm/s with the maximum speed at full load of 22.5 mm/s. The maximum time at maximum pressure is 6 h. The tools can be heated up to 450°C , whereas the FML prototypes were cured under pressure inside the tool at a temperature of 120°C for 2 h.

Fig. 1. Selcom EBX400 glass fiber fabric with texturized polyester yarns in the vertical direction.

Table 1
Properties of the Selcom EBX400 E-glass fiber fabric [17].

Density ρ_f in kg/m^3	Areal weight A_w in g/m^2
2560	408

Table 2
Mix ratio of the epoxy prepreg system 2 [18].

Components	Parts per weight
Araldite® LY 1556	100
Aradur 1571	23
Accelerator 1573	5
Hardener XB 3403	12

Table 3

Properties of epoxy prepreg system Araldite LY 1556 / Aradur 1571 / 1573 / Hardener XB 3403, system 2 mix [18].

Initial mix viscosity, at 25 °C	4000 mPas–6000 mPas
Gel time, at 120 °C	7 min–9 min
Glass transition temperature T_g , curing after B-stage: 2 h, 120 °C	110 °C–115 °C
Density ρ_m	1150 in kg/m ³
Flexural strength	127 MPa–137 MPa
Ultimate elongation (flexural)	7 %–9 %
Flexural modulus	2950 MPa–3150 MPa

2.3. Finite element analysis (FEA)

The design simulations comprised simplified dynamic forming analyses and quasi-static structural analyses. These simulations were carried out in ANSYS Workbench and LS-Dyna. Only room temperature data has been considered for process simulation (isothermal, no increasing working temperature during forming) and testing simulation, due to a limited availability of temperature dependent material properties, and further necessary input data, e.g. friction coefficients between two materials.

Draping of GFRP has been simulated at room temperature and only the elastic properties of the uncured, dry glass fiber fabric (non-impregnated, without resin) have been considered. The ANSYS composite tool allows to determine the draped fiber direction, using an energy algorithm and determines the deformations which can undergo the composite ply based on the minimization of shear strain energy.

The sheet metal forming process has been simulated at room temperature. The metallic blank has been modeled as shell (no thickness, plane strain) and only the elastic and elastic-plastic behavior during forming has been investigated, whereas no spring back effect has been considered. The FE model of the tool was built in ANSYS, and the forming process was solved in LS-Dyna.

The structural performance of the laminate has been simulated at room temperature, using the elastic properties of the cured GFRP, and

the elastic properties of the aluminum. The Fiber Metal Laminate was modeled with layered elements and maximum stress has been used as failure criterion. Benchmark data for lower control arm boundary conditions included a misuse test with a near-application load condition with a maximum displacement of 80 mm and a displacement rate of 0.5 mm/s.

2.4. Compaction testing

For the compaction test, ten dry (non-impregnated, without resin) biaxial layers, i.e. the fiber-reinforcement depicted in Fig. 1, have been stacked on a circular plate with a diameter of 40 mm and compacted using a tensile testing machine from MTS with a capacity of up to 10 kN.

Fig. 2. Stress-strain curves for AA6082-T6 and AA6181-T6 [2].

Fig. 4. AP&T 1200 ton multi-purpose press.

Fig. 3. Schematic illustration of stack with aluminum, prepreg and polyester liner.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Design

3.1.1. Structural requirements and concept

The design solution for the demonstrator was developed towards a weight reduction of 35 % and equivalent stiffness to the original lower control arm made of steel. The boundary conditions included a fixed design space of approx. 399 mm × 344 mm × 42 mm and three load introduction points with fixed location, i.e. two fully fixed surfaces (cylindrical surface axed along x-axis at point C and cylindrical surface axed along z-axis at point B in Fig. 5a)) and one lateral load in x-direction (point A in Fig. 5a)). After determining a design which fulfills the requirement of weight and stiffness, the next step is to assure that the design to be manufacturable via a press operation (body) and CNC (ends, adapters resp.).

The demonstrator is made of several parts, depicted in Fig. 5b), including the body (in green) and three connecting adapters (end parts in purple) of aluminum, connected through adhesive bonding. The body consists of two (one flat and one curved) sandwich structures with outer skins of aluminum with a thickness of 0.8 mm with the aim to avoid local buckling, and a core of glass/epoxy composite laminate with a thickness of 1.9 mm, see Fig. 5b), and a volume fraction of $V_f = 53\%$. The balanced and symmetrical glass/epoxy composite laminate is made of 12 layers (with a thickness per layer of 0.158 mm) with the layup $[0_2/90_2/45/-45]_s$, see Fig. 5c).

3.1.2. Tool

The tool design followed the demonstrator to be manufactured. The open die design, see Fig. 6, consists of a male part installed on top (Fig. 6 top), and a female part installed at the bottom of the press table (Fig. 6 bottom), both made of steel and manufactured by Nordtool AB.

Both parts of the die are separated by two (replaceable) spacer plates

(in blue in Fig. 6a) top) with a (adjustable) thickness of 3.5 mm. The alignment is realized via four guiding rods in the male tool and bushings in the female counterpart. Three adjustable blank holders are located on the female part to position the blank, hybrid layup resp., to be manufactured. Both parts have integrated thermoelements serving as temperature sensors as well as heaters to allow for a controlled heating of the tools up to the curing temperature of 120 °C.

3.2. Fiber reinforcement forming

3.2.1. Compaction testing

In order to investigate the effect of forming, pressing resp., compaction testing of ten dry (non-impregnated, without resin) biaxial layers has been carried out beforehand to define the appropriate process window regarding applied pressure, related thickness reduction, and fiber volume fraction (to identify the material parameters via reverse identification [11]) [22]. The related displacement, reduction in thickness (compaction resp.) is shown in Fig. 7a), taking into account the compliance of the testing machine [23]. The pressure is determined by referring the applied force to the cross section of the circular plate. The fiber volume fraction (FVF, V_f) can be determined using Eq. (1) [24].

$$V_f = \frac{A_w n}{t \rho_f} \quad (1)$$

with A_w representing fiber areal weight (mass per area per ply, see Table 1), n number of plies, t measured thickness during compaction testing, and ρ_f the fiber density (Table 1). The resulting increasing fiber volume fraction with increasing pressure is depicted in Fig. 7b), converging towards 70 %. The calculated thickness per layer is 0.159 mm, resulting in a thickness of 1.91 mm for a laminate of 12 layers, for a volume fraction of $V_f = 50\%$.

A comparison between compaction testing of ten dry biaxial layers and burn-off method (after removal of aluminum skins) used for deter-

Fig. 5. a) Overview with scale b) Exploded view of final design upside down c) Sectional view of final design and materials used, FML modeled with layered elements.

Fig. 6. Tool – Male (top), Female (Bottom) a) Design space b) As manufactured and installed in press.

Fig. 7. Compaction testing a) Thickness reduction vs. applied pressure b) Applied pressure vs. fiber volume fraction c) Thickness per layer vs. fiber volume fraction and comparison to FML (hybrid).

mination of fiber volume fraction of a flat FML is shown in Fig. 7c). The thickness of the FML with aluminum skins with thickness of 0.8 mm on each side, is 3.55 mm, consisting of six biaxial layers (12 UD layers resp.), resulting in a thickness per layer of 0.163 mm. The resulting average measured fiber volume fraction is $V_f = 46\%$, determined via burn-off method (procedure G in [25]).

The difference of 3 % between compaction testing of a dry layup and burn-off method of a prepreg (of a FML) also results from excluding porosity, variations in areal weight, and the use of polyester liner on each side of the prepreg.

3.2.2. Draping

To understand the fiber reorientation during the pressing process, and the initial placement of the GFRP, a draping simulation has been carried out, see Fig. 8a). The theoretical 0°-fiber direction for the

composite laminate is set to follow the length of the wide leg. However, due to the curvatures of the demonstrator, the fiber orientation has to be corrected. A comparison to a pressed dry glass fiber fabric with six biaxial layers is shown in Fig. 8.

3.3. Sheet metal forming

Before three-dimensional forming of metal sheets of thickness 0.8 mm, simple forming analyses have been carried out regarding blank geometry and formability to reduce typical forming artifacts such as wrinkling and cracking [26]. The simulation results are shown in three steps in Fig. 9, starting from placement of the blank in Fig. 9a) (compare to Fig. 12c)), to filling the die depicted in Fig. 9b) and c).

A comparison between simulation and an aluminum blank after forming is shown in Fig. 10, depicting the high strains at the radius

Fig. 8. a) Draped fiber direction from simulation b) Dry glass fiber fabric after forming operation.

Fig. 9. Simulation of forming of blanks a) Initial stage b) Intermediate stage c) Final stage.

Fig. 10. Comparison between a) Forming simulation and b) Forming trial on AA6181.

between the legs, Fig. 10a), leading to crack formation, see Fig. 10b).

To understand the elastic-plastic forming behavior of the aluminum in different areas of the blanks to be formed, with different forming degrees, a Forming Limit diagram (FLD), provided by the simulation, has been considered. Fig. 11a) depicts the relatively low multi-axiality of the forming process (compare to uniaxial tensile testing). Formability limits by fracture in sheet metal forming have been taken from [2,27]. Fig. 11 a) depicts high strains representing critical areas that might lead to crack formation. The selected critical point in Fig. 11a) represents an element taken within the radius between the legs, shown in Fig. 10a). As can be seen from the forming limit for AA6181 in heat treatment state T4 (naturally aged), depicted in Fig. 10a), cracking would happen. The aluminum sheets used in this study were delivered in heat treatment state T6 (artificially aged), with a stronger and less ductile state

compared to T4. Aiming to increase the malleability, additional heat treatment, i.e., soft-annealing at 300 °C for 4 h, has been carried out. The qualitative stress-elongation curves depicted in Fig. 11b) prove that additional soft annealing leads to an increase in ductility by a factor of approx. two to the cost of strength by a reduction of approx. 50 % in uniaxial tension, in comparison to heat treatment state T6 (artificially aged).

The sheet metal forming simulations indicated risks of material failure in the area between the legs, see Fig. 10a). Therefore, the blank geometry was adjusted and aluminum blanks with a thickness of 0.8 mm were waterjet cut, see Fig. 12. Those preliminary forming trials were carried out to be able to identify challenges and approaches for solving these before manufacturing the demonstrator.

The outer surface of the blanks was taped with polyethylene tape, see

Fig. 11. a) Identifying hot spots using a Forming Limit Diagram (FLD) b) Normalized stress-elongation curves and the effect of heat treatment from artificially aged (T6) to soft-annealed.

Fig. 12b), to enable easy removal of “Tribotextil” and excess resin after forming.

Several forming trials have been carried out regarding blank geometry, including changes in the radius between the narrow and wide leg, material at the borders, and soft-annealing of the blanks. In addition, different lubrications between tool and blanks have been investigated. The blank geometries used for the forming trials are sketched in Fig. 13. Those geometries with more material on the perimeter as well as different amounts of material between the legs, see Fig. 13c)–e), ensure to have sufficient material to be able to cut out the nominal geometry after forming and to minimize the risk of cracks in the region of the nominal geometry and wrinkling.

One aspect of the design rule for modification of the blank geometry focused on reducing strain in the aluminum blank aiming for a reduction of crack propagation between the legs, rather than preventing crack initiation (since the region will be cut out because it is outside the designed shape of the demonstrator). A simplified topology and notch shape optimization was employed, followed by iterative trial and error tests. As a result, the shape of the aluminum blank was adjusted to achieve the best fit between the formed blank and the designed shape of the demonstrator.

The initial forming trials, shown in Fig. 14, did confirm the risks highlighted in the forming simulations and cracks in the aluminum blank were observed in the area between the legs.

From those preliminary investigations, it can be concluded that soft-annealing via heat treating the aluminum sheets at 300 °C for 4 h lead to an increase in formability, see Fig. 14a). Furthermore, the use of “Tribotextil” between steel die surface and aluminum blanks improves formability and reduces the risk for cracks compared to regular drawing oil, see Fig. 14b). In addition, leaving more material between the legs (no radius resp.) reduces the risk for crack formation but increases wrinkling in the formed part, see Fig. 14c) right.

3.4. Hybrid manufacturing

Simulating the entire FML forming process is feasible, provided the necessary input data is available. The influence of temperature on material data is crucial, and accurate friction coefficients between GFRP, aluminum, and steel (of the metal die surface) are required, among others, to enable comprehensive and thorough simulations. Acquiring such data would necessitate an extensive experimental campaign. Given the constraints of experimental properties and resources, former sections focused on separate analyses of draping and metal forming. Draping simulation, even when simplified with dry glass fiber fabric, demonstrated feasibility, allowing the emphasis to shift to the most critical aspect, being aluminum sheet forming. The following purely

experimental study integrates both processes simultaneously, draping and metal forming, incorporating additional pressing and friction assistance through “Tribotextil”, along with the use of wet (impregnated) glass fiber fabric, and polyester liner to enhance bonding between metal and fabric. These aspects have not yet been explored through numerical simulations. Therefore, further and more complex investigations and simulations are essential, which will be presented in the conclusions' section.

3.4.1. Flat fiber metal laminate

The GFRP prepreg with layup $[(0/90)_2/\pm 45]_s$ $[(0/90/0/90/+45/-45/-45/+45/90/0/90/0)]$ was placed between two 0.8 mm thick AA6082-T6 aluminum blanks. In addition, two layers of polyester liner were added on a top and a bottom of the GFRP (Fig. 3), to create a resin rich layer for improved bonding to the aluminum. Beforehand, an alkaline washing was performed manually on the aluminum blanks to facilitate the adhesion between the resin and the aluminum layers. To control the thickness of the laminate during pressing, shims of thickness 1.85 mm were placed between the aluminum on each side of the prepreg. The stack was then placed in a heated flat tool, with a temperature of 120 °C, and pressed with the settings built-in stepwise. The five steps were set to: 221 kN in 60 s, 226 kN in 40 s, 231 kN in 100 s, 236 kN in 100 s, and finally at maximum force at 316 kN in 6840 s, resulting in a processing duration of almost 2 h. Directly after the press operation the FML was removed from the tool and additionally cooled in air, see Fig. 15a).

The total average thickness of approx. 3.5 mm resulted in a volume fraction of aluminum of $V_{Al} = 45\%$ and GFRP of $V_{GFRP} = 55\%$. This results in an average thickness/layer of 0.158 mm (for 12 UD layers) and an average fiber volume fraction of $V_f = 45.8\%$ for GFRP, compare to compaction testing results depicted in Fig. 7c). A representative nominal tensile stress – axial strain curve for FML in comparison to the aluminum is shown in Fig. 15b) [20,28]. The initial deformation is characterized by the elastic deformation of both constituents, followed by the onset of plastification of the aluminum, and the failure of the GFRP core. The deformation and sequential failure of each aluminum skin represent the final stages. See [20] for detailed investigation under quasi-static and cyclic loading for both, GFRP and FML.

3.4.2. Curved fiber metal laminate

When pressing the curved FML, the same material layup using AA6181 (soft-annealed) was used as for the flat FML (Fig. 3). The press force was 200 kN throughout the curing cycle and no additional shims were used, since the tool has integrated spacers of 3.5 mm (Fig. 6) allowing for a nominal layup thickness, and to avoid over-compressing the laminate. To prevent local thinning and cracking of the aluminum

Fig. 12. Aluminum blank a) Waterjet cut b) Outer surface with polyethylene tape c) Before forming.

Fig. 13. Waterjet cut blank geometries (b) Manually cut).

Fig. 14. a) Effect of heat treatment during forming of a single aluminum blank, left: T6 as delivered, right: soft-annealed b) Effect of lubricant between tool and aluminum during simultaneous forming of two aluminum blanks with dry fiber reinforcements in between, left: regular drawing oil, right: "Tribotextil" c) Effect of blank geometry, left: less material but cracks, right: more material (no radius), no cracks but wrinkles.

blanks during forming, "Tribotextil" was placed on each side of the part between the steel die surface and the aluminum to facilitate the sheet metal forming process, see Fig. 16.

Fig. 17a) and b) depict the part as manufactured after removal from the tool, see Fig. 16b), and removal of "Tribotextil" and excess resin on the outer surfaces of the aluminum, which was facilitated using a polyethylene tape, see Fig. 12b).

The blank geometry illustrated in Fig. 13d) resulted in the best formed parts, although a crack occurred using this geometry. Since its location is outside the area of interest, the crack will be trimmed. A comparison between the initial blank geometry from Fig. 13a) and the final blank geometry from Fig. 13d), used for the demonstrator, is shown in Fig. 18.

A quantitative quality metric regarding geometric deviation between design and final product is depicted in Fig. 19c) and d), ranging below

Fig. 15. a) Manufactured flat FML b) Tensile stress – strain curve for FML and aluminum [1].

Fig. 16. Pressing operation a) Multi-material layup, including “Tribotextil” between the blanks and die surfaces b) Formed part ready for removal from tool.

Fig. 17. 3D-FML a) After removal of “Tribotextil” b) Prior to edge trimming.

± 1 mm for the part of a design space of 399 mm × 344 mm × 42 mm (using GOM Inspect Professional 2019).

3.5. Assembly and structural performance

Both parts, flat and curved, were edge trimmed and cut with a band saw to near net shapes, see Fig. 19, and grinded using templates for guidance. After positioning both parts, the position was locked using two M3 screws. The function of the positioning screws is to prevent sliding and secure that both parts are positioned correctly to each other during bonding along the thin bond line, see Fig. 20a). Three aluminum

adapters for load introduction were manufactured by Nordtool AB. Prior to bonding, all aluminum parts were cleaned with alkaline detergent and checked with a water-break test to secure good adhesion properties. Adhesive was applied to all bonding surfaces in one operation using a pneumatic disposing gun for 2K-adhesive with static mixer. The adhesive used was Huntsman Araldite 2019 280 ml [29].

The three adapters, with adhesive on the bonding areas, were placed in the curved FML, then the flat FML was positioned using two M3 positioning screws, see highlighted areas Fig. 20c). The assembly was then clamped using C-clamps, see Fig. 20b), while removing excess adhesive along the bond lines. When clamped in final position and wiped clean from excess adhesive, the assembly was cured in an oven at

Fig. 18. Effect of blank geometry a) Initial blank geometry b) Final blank geometry for the demonstrator.

Fig. 19. Difference CAD model part – manufactured part a) Top view b) Bottom view.

80 °C for 4 h, see Fig. 20b). The demonstrator ready for testing is shown in Fig. 20d).

The structural performance of the demonstrator has been determined

via a quasi-static destructive misuse test. The test rig has been designed to ensure minimal compliance in the clamping section, see Fig. 21a) right side. The test rig was made of 160 mm × 80 mm × 5 mm steel

a)

b)

c)

d)

Fig. 20. a) Bond line for both parts b) Clamped and bonded assembly placed in oven c) Bottom view highlighting the M3 screws (red circles) used for positioning during bonding d) Final demonstrator.

profiles, which were welded to 15 mm thick steel plate. Spacers were manufactured to take up the slack in the bushings to reduce their motion.

The vertical displacement-controlled loading of 0.5 mm/s aims for a deformation of 80 mm before failure. The load introduction has been realized by an actuator with a maximum stroke of 380 mm from top downwards (Fig. 21a) left side) and force has been determined using a 250 kN load cell. Linear potentiometers built into the actuator (400 mm) have been used to determine the vertical displacement at load introduction. Digital Image Correlation (DIC) has been used for full-field measurement of displacements [30], using a GOM Aramis stereo-DIC system with 6 Mpx cameras and 12.5 mm focal length lenses. The stand-off distance was set to 690 mm, and the stereo angle was 25° with a camera distance of 267 mm. Besides marker dots for determination of three-dimensional displacement, a speckle pattern has been applied, see Fig. 21b).

A comparison between simulation and experiment is shown in Fig. 21c) and d) at the same force, compare also to load-displacement curve and circles (deformation at same force for simulation and experiment) shown in Fig. 22. The same boundary conditions as in the test are used for the simulation. The aimed maximum displacement of 80 mm has not been reached before collapse. In addition, Fig. 22 depicts that the measured out-of-plane motion is larger than the measured in-plane horizontal motion.

The failure is shown Fig. 23, depicting the cause of the instability is based on the debonding of the lower FML from the curved FML within the adhesive joint.

As shown in Fig. 20a), the bond line width is relatively small due to the design constraints. The hot spot located at the connection between

parts could also be detected in the simulation.

4. Conclusions

This contribution described a methodology and feasibility study for successful development, design, and manufacturing of a three-dimensional Fiber Metal Laminate (FML) suitable for e.g. EV chassis parts. The prototypical demonstrator represents a lightweight multi-material solution, serving as a potential replacement of an existing steel solution for a lower control arm. The development of the multi-material solution included an asymmetrical three-dimensional Fiber Metal Laminate structure with outer skins consisting of a recycled aluminum alloy, and the inner core of a Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer composite. The aim of this study was to present a simple simulation methodology for process manufacturing and part performance to reduce the developing time.

Process simulation supported the experimental investigations on damage caused by the manufacturing process of sheet metal forming, and on fiber reorientation during draping. Initial trials of sheet metal forming did confirm the risks highlighted in the forming simulations, where cracks in the aluminum blanks were observed. It could be shown that soft-annealing of the aluminum is necessary to increase formability, leading to a reduction of crack propagation. In addition, the use of the low-friction textile “Tribotextil” [21] between steel tool and aluminum blanks improved formability and reduced the risk for crack formation.

The separate FEA simulations for GFRP draping and aluminum forming were performed to capture the distinct deformation behavior of each constituent material under forming conditions. This implies deformation behavior of aluminum from the aspect of wrinkling and

a)

b)

c)

d)

Fig. 21. a) Experiment setup using stereo-DIC b) Reference image using marker dots and spray-painted speckle pattern. Displacement results at c) Vertical displacement (x-direction) of 18.2 mm and 4.99 kN from simulation d) Vertical displacement (y-direction) of 21.2 mm and 4.99 kN from experiment.

Fig. 22. Load-displacement curve from testing of the demonstrator.

fracture as well as fiber reorientation for GFRP. It has to be acknowledged that the deformation behavior of aluminum within an FML differs from that of aluminum alone. The approach shown aimed to systematically analyze the individual forming characteristics before integrating them into the manufacturing process design. The results proved that the approach was successful regarding manufacturing of an asymmetric 3D-FML, although not all the details have been incorporated in the modeling and simulation.

Based on the unresolved challenges faced in this study, important considerations in process simulation of FML are summarized in the following.

Challenges in forming FML structures include springback, wrinkling and cracking, thickness variation, and delamination [6], affecting the mechanical properties throughout the structure [31]. The results presented in [12] show the challenges of hybrid forming where the interaction between fabric layers and metal sheets limit the forming behavior of the latter. The plastic deformation of the metal sheets is increased by the fabric and the draping of the fabric is affected by the metal sheets, which results in wrinkling in both constituents. The likelihood of fracture in both constituents is increased with increasing drawing depth or complexity of the geometry [12]. Therefore, more advanced material constitutive models for both constituents and interfacial models are desired to capture fracture initiation and corresponding forming limits as well as to accurately account for ply-ply slip [6,12]. Since the failure

in hybrid materials is very complex and not always visible from the outside, more complex criteria also considering internal failure have to be defined and incorporated in the future [32].

In [11], process simulation is compared to an experimental setup for combined deep-drawing and infiltration, where dry deep-drawing trials with a metal sheet and the hybrid stack were conducted. Heat transfer and curing need to be implemented in numerical models to capture the rapidly changing viscosity during processing [11] (see [33] for temperature dependent curing time and viscosity), as the matrix viscosity increases during polymerization. An increased viscosity reduces friction (being highest for dry fabrics) between fabric and metal, which improves formability [14] and prevents sheet elongation during forming. Therefore, measuring friction coefficients between fibers and metal sheets is essential [14], and need to be incorporated in numerical models.

In addition, [13] highlights that the tension-compression anisotropy of the fabric is needed for modeling the combined forming of metal and fabric, where the stiffness of the metal dominates the draping process.

The manufacturing temperature was chosen/adapted to the curing temperature of the polymer, rather than to facilitate forming of the aluminum, which is common [6]. The temperature of 120 °C during manufacturing is considered cold forming for aluminum alloys. It is expected that ultimate tensile strength of AA6082-T6 decreases less than 10 % at 120 °C compared to RT [34]. In comparison, soft-annealing, done in this study to enhance formability, leads to a decrease in ultimate tensile strength of almost 50 % (with an increase in ductility by a factor of approx. two) in comparison to heat treatment state T6 (artificially aged). This effect is considered to be more severe. For a future thorough numerical investigation, temperature dependent material behavior (thermo-mechanical properties) has to be taken into account, which also includes time- and temperature-dependent work hardening during forming of aluminum.

The process time for manufacturing the FML was approx. 2 h, which could be reduced to a few minutes, when using a faster curing resin. An alternative approach could be a partial curing of the component in the press followed by a simultaneous curing of multiple components in an oven. Based on preliminary investigations, this process optimization leads to a reduction of processing time from 2 h to approx. 18 min followed by post curing with a duration up to 4 h.

Structural analysis and modeling were carried out as a misuse test and simulation with near-application loading based on benchmark data for lower control arm boundary conditions. Due to debonding between flat and curved FML, optimization strategies are necessary to improve the structural performance regarding adhesive bonding, e.g. by increasing bond line area or using an additional e.g., hemming process.

a)

b)

Fig. 23. Postmortem investigation of the demonstrator a) Front view b) Side view with debonding.

Changes in the geometric design could be another option, respecting restrictions due to the allowable design space.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Matthias Merzkirch: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Erwan Juin:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jesper Eman:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jocke Pettersson:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Magdalena Juntikka:** Writing – original draft, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Fredrik Ahlqvist:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Olof Säfvenberg:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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